

CHINESE NETIZENS' PERCEPTUAL ATTITUDES TOWARD UZBEK PILAF AND ITS IMPACT ON TOURISM ECONOMY: A CASE STUDY OF BULLET COMMENTS AND USER REVIEWS ON BILIBILI TRAVEL VIDEOS

Liang Quan

Silk Road International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage, Samarkand, Ph.D student
in Economics of Service Industries

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15599411>

Abstract. *In recent years, with the advancement of the Belt and Road Initiative, Central Asian countries have gradually entered the field of vision of Chinese tourists. As a key node along the Silk Road, Uzbekistan has attracted the attention of Chinese netizens due to its unique culinary culture and tourism resources. This study examines bullet comments on travel videos featuring Uzbek cuisine on Bilibili, employing text analysis to explore Chinese netizens' perceptual attitudes toward Uzbek food and its influence on tourism economy. The findings reveal that Chinese netizens' perceptions of Uzbek cuisine primarily revolve around three dimensions: "exotic curiosity," "cultural affinity," and "economic value for money." These perceptions further shape potential tourists' travel intentions and consumption behaviors. The study provides theoretical insights for cross-cultural culinary tourism marketing. It recommends that governments leverage the integration of gastronomy and tourism by strengthening policy guidance and dynamic regulation while improving supporting services. Additionally, embedding cultural and creative elements and enhancing social engagement features can increase the average spending per culinary tourist and extend their stay. By synergizing with local cultural and tourism resources, stakeholders should foster industrial chain collaboration, integrating food tourism into regional economic development to offer more diverse and higher-value-added culinary tourism products.*

Keywords: *culinary tourism, Belt and Road Initiative, Bilibili bullet comments, text analysis, local government cultural-tourism integration.*

Annotatsiya. *So‘nggi yillarda “Bir kamar, bir yo‘l” tashabbusi rivojlanishi bilan Markaziy Osiyo mamlakatlari Xitoy sayyohlarining e‘tiboriga tushdi. Buyuk ipak yo‘lining muhim tuguni bo‘lgan O‘zbekiston o‘zining noyob oshpazlik madaniyati va turistik resurslari bilan xitoylik internet foydalanuvchilarining diqqatini tortmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqotda Bilibili platformasida O‘zbekiston taomlari haqidagi sayohat videolariga qo‘yilgan izohlar (bullet comments) tahlil qilinadi va matn tahlili usullari yordamida xitoylik foydalanuvchilarning O‘zbekiston taomlariga bo‘lgan munosabati va turizm iqtisodiyotiga ta‘siri o‘rganiladi. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, xitoylik foydalanuvchilarning O‘zbekiston taomlariga bo‘lgan qarashlari asosan uch jihatga qaratilgan: “ekzotik qiziqish”, “madaniy yaqinlik” va “arzon narx sifat nisbati”. Bu omillar potensial sayyohlarning sayohat qilish niyatlari va iste‘molchi xatti-harakatlarini shakllantiradi. Tadqiqot gastro-turizmning madaniyatlararo marketingi uchun nazariy natijalar taqdim etadi. Hukumatlarga ovqat va turizmni integratsiyalash orqali siyosiy yo‘naltirish va dinamik tartibga solishni mustahkamlash, shuningdek, yordamchi xizmatlarni yaxshilash tavsiya etiladi. Bundan tashqari, madaniy va kreativ elementlarni joriy etish hamda ijtimoiy ishtirokni oshirish gastro-turistlarning o‘rtacha xarajatlarini ko‘paytirishi va ularning qolish muddatini uzaytirishi mumkin. Mahalliy madaniy va turistik resurslar bilan sinergiyada*

ishtirok etuvchi tomonlar sanoat zanjiri hamkorligini rivojlantirishi, gastro-turizmni mintaqaviy iqtisodiy rivojlanishga integratsiyalashi va yanada xilma-xil yuqori qo'shilgan qiymatga ega gastro-turistik mahsulotlarni taklif qilishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: *gastro-turizm, "Bir kamar, bir yo'l" tashabbusi, Bilibili izohlari (bullet comments), matn tahlili, mahalliy hokimiyat tomonidan madaniyat va turizmni integratsiyalash.*

Аннотация. *В последние годы, с развитием инициативы «Один пояс – один путь», страны Центральной Азии постепенно вошли в поле зрения китайских туристов. Узбекистан, являясь ключевым узлом Великого шелкового пути, привлекает внимание китайских интернет-пользователей благодаря своей уникальной кулинарной культуре и туристическим ресурсам. В данном исследовании анализируются комментарии (bullet comments) к видео о путешествиях, посвященных узбекской кухне, на платформе Bilibili, с применением текстового анализа для изучения восприятия китайскими пользователями узбекской кухни и ее влияния на туристическую экономику. Результаты показывают, что восприятие узбекской кухни китайскими пользователями в основном сосредоточено вокруг трех аспектов: «экзотическая любознательность», «культурная близость» и «экономическая выгода». Эти факторы формируют туристические намерения и потребительское поведение потенциальных туристов. Исследование предоставляет теоретические выводы для межкультурного маркетинга гастрономического туризма. Рекомендуется, чтобы правительства использовали интеграцию гастрономии и туризма, укрепляя политическое руководство и динамическое регулирование, а также улучшая сопутствующие услуги. Кроме того, внедрение культурно-креативных элементов и усиление социальной вовлеченности может увеличить средние расходы гастрономических туристов и продлить их пребывание. Путем синергии с местными культурными и туристическими ресурсами заинтересованные стороны должны способствовать сотрудничеству в рамках производственной цепочки, интегрируя гастрономический туризм в региональное экономическое развитие, чтобы предлагать более разнообразные и высокодоходные туристические продукты.*

Ключевые слова: *гастрономический туризм, инициатива "Один пояс – один путь", комментарии на Bilibili (bullet comments), текстовый анализ, интеграция культуры и туризма местными властями.*

1. Introduction

Uzbekistan, located in Central Asia, was once a vital hub along the ancient Silk Road. Its culinary culture integrates diverse influences, including Turkic, Persian, and Russian elements. Signature dishes such as Plov (pilaf), Samsa (stuffed pastries), and Lagman (noodle soup) have gradually gained international recognition. In recent years, with the deepening of economic and trade relations between China and Central Asian countries, Uzbekistan has implemented an e-visa facilitation policy for Chinese tourists, encouraging more Chinese travelers to consider it as a tourism destination.

Bilibili, a video platform popular among young Chinese users, features a bullet comment function that provides real-time, intuitive user feedback. This data reflects netizens' emotional tendencies and cognitive patterns regarding specific topics. By analyzing bullet comment texts from relevant Bilibili videos, this study explores Chinese netizens' perceptions of Uzbek cuisine and examines its potential impact on the tourism economy.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Development and Evolving Connotations of Culinary Tourism

Research on culinary tourism began in the 1980s when Belisle (1983) first proposed the idea of food as a tourism attraction, emphasizing its role in cultural experiences. Over time, scholars have offered diverse definitions. Wolf and Erik (2002) defined it as "tourists' pursuit of unique food experiences," while Hall and Sharples (2003) highlighted the centrality of gastronomic experiences, such as visiting food-producing regions, participating in culinary events, or dining at specialty restaurants. Long (2004) argued that culinary tourism encompasses all food-related activities—physiological, social, cultural, economic, spiritual, and aesthetic—that tourists intentionally engage in when exploring foreign culinary systems, indicating that it transcends mere sustenance and evolves into a broader experiential pursuit.

More recently, Ellis (2018) approached culinary tourism from an anthropological perspective, viewing it as a medium for interaction between tourists and destinations, emphasizing its role in cultural communication. Local cuisine, in this view, serves as an authentic representation of cultural identity. Contemporary scholars increasingly regard culinary tourism as a holistic, multisensory experience, shaped by the interplay between sensory stimuli (e.g., sight, sound, smell, taste, touch) and non-sensory factors (e.g., cognition and emotion) (Muskat, 2024).

As tourism consumption shifts from material needs to spiritual fulfillment, food has evolved beyond mere nourishment into a carrier of cultural imagery and historical memory, becoming a core attraction for destinations. In this process, food not only triggers immediate sensory responses but also fosters deeper cultural understanding and emotional resonance through cognitive processing. Thus, the essence of culinary tourism lies in tourists' active pursuit of meaning, where bodily perception and psychological interpretation dynamically interact to establish a connection between the self and the destination's culture, ultimately forming a multidimensional experience that blends sensory pleasure with intellectual satisfaction (Sanchez, 2012). Although definitions vary, scholars generally agree that culinary tourism is a comprehensive activity integrating sensory enjoyment, cultural exploration, and economic engagement.

2.2 Destination Image Construction and New Media Marketing

Short-video platforms have become crucial tools for culinary tourism marketing. Xie and Shi (2024), in their study of Yangshuo West Street, found that Douyin (TikTok) videos significantly enhanced tourists' recommendation intentions by shaping cognitive images (e.g., food quality, specialty dishes) and emotional attitudes. However, Wu (2023) noted in their research on Chengdu that while food-related short videos reinforce emotional connections and cultural identity, they may also create unrealistic expectations. Meanwhile, Tao et al. (2025) observed that Jiuquan's culinary branding heavily relies on lamb dishes, yet fails to sufficiently promote local ingredients (e.g., sand leeks), reflecting a lack of diversified food supply. Dong (2025) further suggested that short videos should focus on immersive storytelling and authenticity to bridge the gap between tourists' expectations and actual experiences.

2.3 Applicability of Bullet Comment Text Analysis

Bullet comments represent a real-time, fragmented form of user expression, capturing viewers' emotional responses. In today's fast-paced digital culture, watching food-related videos is fundamentally a process of transitioning from visual perception to symbolic consumption. As carriers of cultural information, symbols play a crucial role in emotion transmission and shared meaning—without symbolic mediation, individual experiences risk becoming isolated and inexpressible.

Food videos employ dual coding—combining visual symbols (e.g., color, composition) with cultural symbols (e.g., regional characteristics, cooking techniques)—to construct an emotional sanctuary. Within this symbolic space, viewers immerse themselves, temporarily escaping real-life pressures and finding psychological solace in virtual culinary experiences. Thus, bullet comments can be seen as an interactive medium between individuals and food videos (Peng, 2023).

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

The study collected data from Bilibili, a prominent Chinese video-sharing platform, focusing on a high-viewership travel vlog titled "Uzbekistan's Plov: There's No Limit to How Big the Cooking Pot Can Be". A total of 1,800 bullet comments were extracted for analysis.

3.2 Analytical Approach

The research employed a mixed-methods text analysis framework to examine user-generated content. First, keyword extraction was conducted using Python’s Jieba library to identify high-frequency terms (e.g., "plov," "samsa," "spices," "affordable"). Next, sentiment analysis was performed via the SnowNLP library to classify comments into positive, neutral, and negative emotional tones. Finally, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic modeling was applied to uncover dominant thematic patterns within the bullet comment discourse.

4. Research Findings

4.1 Chinese Netizens’ Perceptual Dimensions of Uzbek Cuisine

Category	Bullet Comment Content	Notes
Humor & Satire	"Chickpeas are too dry and hard—covering them with a bowl steams them faster"	Exaggerated description of cooking method.
	"Every time they cook, a family loses their door plank"	Satirizes the practice of burning door planks, showing cultural differences in food perceptions.
Technical Discussion	"This half-covered lid effect is perfect—allows some steam to escape while still cooking the rice"	Discusses the functionality of the lid.
	"Salt is added when the rice goes in; cumin and peppercorns are added with the chickpeas"	Detailed explanation of seasoning timing.
Cultural Comparison	"Much cleaner than how they do it in India"	Compares Uzbek plov with Indian cooking, emphasizing hygiene differences.
	"Very similar to Xinjiang-style plov"	Highlights regional similarities in plov preparation.

Category	Bullet Comment Content	Notes
Ingredients & Techniques	"Yellow carrots, red ones are actually yellow carrots"	Notes ingredient diversity.
	"Chickpeas take longer to cook—covering them with a bowl helps"	Practical cooking tip.
Hygiene & Health	"At least they wear gloves—much cleaner than in India"	Positive remark on hygiene standards.
	"So greasy...how is this appetizing?"	Health concerns about oily food.
Visual & Artistic	"This meal has strong artistic vibes"	Aesthetic appreciation of the cooking process.
	"Does the fire from carved door planks smell like art?"	Creative blend of art and cooking.
Personal Experience	"Tried it—insanely delicious, but hard to find in most places"	Positive personal review.
	"Honestly, this plov looks mediocre, and the taste isn't anything special"	Negative personal critique.

Through textual analysis, the bullet comments were found to primarily revolve around three key dimensions:

Exotic Curiosity (35%):

Netizens exhibited strong interest in Uzbekistan's unique cooking methods (e.g., large-cauldron plov) and spice usage (e.g., cumin, saffron). Representative comments included: "Why is this rice yellow?" "Do they really eat with their hands?"

Cultural Affinity (40%):

Due to historical Silk Road exchanges, many netizens perceived Uzbek cuisine as similar to Xinjiang cuisine in China. Typical comments noted: "These samsa pastries look just like Xinjiang's!" "Lagman noodles seem like a variant of Northwest Chinese pulled noodles."

Economic Value-for-Money (25%):

A significant portion of comments focused on food affordability, such as: "How is this huge plate of plov only 10 RMB?" "Eating in Uzbekistan is cheaper than having Xinjiang food in China!"

4.2 Sentiment Analysis and Travel Intentions

Sentiment analysis revealed that 65% of comments were positive, 30% neutral, and only 5% negative. Negative remarks primarily concerned hygiene worries (e.g., "Would street vendors cause food poisoning?").

Crucially, positive sentiment correlated strongly with travel intention, particularly in comments discussing economic value-for-money. Phrases like "I want to visit!" and "Next trip destination decided!" frequently appeared, suggesting that cost-effective dining experiences significantly enhance destination appeal.

5. Discussion and Recommendations

Implications for Uzbekistan's Tourism Economy

5.1. In-depth exploration of the uniqueness of Silk Road culinary culture is the primary task for the development of Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism. As the crossroads of Central Asian civilizations, Uzbekistan's culinary culture carries the imprints of Persian, Turkic, Mongol, and other diverse cultural influences. This distinctive historical heritage should be systematically studied and interpreted through cultural anthropological research. It is recommended to establish an interdisciplinary team comprising historians, gastronomists, and tourism experts to conduct scholarly research on the historical origins, ingredient evolution, and culinary techniques of traditional dishes, thereby constructing a comprehensive culinary cultural genealogy. Such academic support will not only enhance the cultural depth of gastronomic tourism but also provide an authoritative content foundation for subsequent marketing and promotion.

5.2. Story-driven marketing is an effective means to showcase the charm of culinary culture. In an era of information overload, mere taste experiences are insufficient to create lasting tourism appeal. Instead, food should be embedded within vivid historical narratives. The "intangible cultural heritage +" communication model can serve as a reference, where each signature dish is paired with a cultural story. For instance, augmented reality (AR) technology could recreate historical scenes of merchants sharing pilaf in Samarkand's bazaars, or a series of micro-documentaries could trace the evolving social functions of samsa (baked dumplings) across different periods. This narrative approach not only satisfies tourists' cognitive needs but also creates a multidimensional experience that transcends mere taste.

5.3. Developing culturally rich food IP requires systematic branding efforts. Uzbekistan can draw lessons from successful cases such as Korean kimchi and Japanese washoku by selecting several representative dishes for standardization and branding. This includes establishing unified preparation standards, designing visual identity systems, and registering trademarks for protection. Notably, IP development should not remain superficial; rather, it should build a comprehensive cultural ecosystem through sustained content output. For instance, developing cultural and creative products centered on cuisine, publishing professional cookbooks, and organizing international food festivals can create diversified IP monetization channels.

5.4. Highlighting the "high cost-performance" advantage is a key strategy for attracting Chinese tourists. Analysis of Bilibili user comments reveals that price-sensitive tourists constitute a significant portion of the target demographic. Tourism promotions should emphasize the exceptional value of local dining, such as by creating price comparison charts between domestic and foreign markets or designing interactive content like the "100-yuan food challenge." Additionally, collaborating with local restaurant associations to introduce "tourist discount meal sets"—offering competitive pricing without compromising quality—can convert price advantages into market competitiveness while avoiding a detrimental race to the bottom.

5.5. Standardizing dining environments is a foundational step in enhancing tourist experiences. Addressing hygiene concerns, which are particularly important to Chinese tourists, requires the adoption of international food safety management systems and tiered certification for restaurants in key tourist cities. A "recommended restaurant" labeling system could be introduced

to officially recognize establishments that meet hygiene standards, provide Chinese menus, and accept mobile payments. Furthermore, increasing operational transparency through live-streamed kitchen operations or open-kitchen designs allows tourists to observe food preparation processes, thereby building consumer confidence.

5.6. Designing social-media-friendly culinary experiences can amplify promotional reach. To cater to younger tourists' sharing preferences, interactive and visually striking food-related activities—such as creating an "oversized plov photo spot" or hosting a "best food selfie" competition—should be developed. These initiatives must strike a balance between engagement and shareability, preserving cultural authenticity while allowing sufficient creative freedom for personalized expression. This approach encourages user-generated content and organic dissemination.

5.7. Establishing a word-of-mouth dissemination system is crucial for sustaining long-term appeal. Beyond official promotions, greater emphasis should be placed on sharing authentic tourist experiences. A robust user review mechanism and content incentive program can be implemented to encourage tourists to share their culinary experiences on major social platforms. Simultaneously, a responsive customer service system should be established to promptly address negative feedback, transforming potential crises into opportunities to demonstrate service commitment. This user-centric reputation management strategy helps build enduring brand trust among target demographics.

6. Theoretical Contributions

This study validates the role of the "cultural similarity-difference" framework in food-related tourism decision-making and provides a paradigm for applying bullet-screen comment analysis in tourism research.

7. Conclusion

Through an analysis of Bilibili bullet-screen comments, this paper reveals Chinese netizens' cognitive patterns regarding Uzbek cuisine and their implications for the tourism economy. Future research could incorporate questionnaire surveys to further examine the relationship between bullet-screen data and actual travel behavior.

REFERENCES

1. Belisle, F. J. (1983). Tourism and food production in the Caribbean. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 10(4), 497-513.
2. Hall, C. M., & Sharples, L. (2003). The consumption of experiences or the experience of consumption? An introduction to the tourism of taste. In *Food tourism around the world: Development, management and markets* (pp. 1-24). Butterworth-Heinemann.
3. Long, L. (Ed.). (2004). *Culinary tourism*. The University Press of Kentucky.
4. Ellis, A., Park, E., Kim, S., & Yeoman, I. (2018). What is food tourism? *Tourism Management*, 68, 250-263.
5. Muskat, B., Prayag, G., & Hosany, S. (2024). The interplay of sensory and non-sensory factors in food tourism experiences. *Tourism Review*, 79(3), 658-670.
6. Sanchez-Canizares, S. M., & Lopez-Guzman, T. (2012). Gastronomy as a tourism resource: Profile of the culinary tourist. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 15(3), 229-245.
7. Xie, Y., & Shi, C. Y. (2024). The impact of Douyin short videos on the image of food tourism destinations: A case study of Yangshuo West Street. *Journal of Xichang University (Natural Science Edition)*, 38(4), 61-67.

8. Dan, W. J. (2023). Research on the reshaping of local identity through urban short videos: A case study of Chongqing and Chengdu short videos. **China Television, (11), 50-56.**
9. Tao, L., et al. (2025). Research on the development of Jiuquan food tourism based on online text analysis. **China Food Safety Magazine, (8), 172-175.**
10. Dong, Y. J., & Zhang, M. J. (2025). The influence of perceived value of food short videos on tourists' behavioral intentions: The mediating role of flow experience and trust. **Price: Theory & Practice, 1-5.**
11. Peng, F. H. (2023). Analysis of users' emotional experience in bullet-screen comments on food short videos: A text analysis based on Bilibili food channel "Mianyang Cuisine." *New Media Research, 9(6), 28-32.*